

The Influence of Work Stress on Counterproductive Work Behavior: A Modified Role of Emotional Intelligence (Centre for Lombok District Health Service Staff Study)

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Abstract:- This research aims to examine the moderating influence of Emotional Intelligence (EI) on Work Stress (WS) on Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB). CWB is work deviation behavior that is not in accordance with organizational norms and rules, and is detrimental to both the organization and the individual himself. This type of research is causal associative research with a quantitative approach. The data collection technique used the census method with a population of 112 respondents from Central Lombok District Health Service employees. Data were analyzed using the Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) technique with Smart PLS 4 software. The results showed that Work Stress had a significant positive effect on Counterproductive Work Behavior with a coefficient value of 0.713, a t statistic value of 16.932 > 1.96, and P value 0.000 < 0.05, and Emotional Intelligence does not weaken (moderate) the influence of work stress on Counterproductive Work Behavior with a coefficient value of -0.58, t statistic value 1.275 < 1.96, and P value 0.393 < 0.05. Every employee has a different response to stressors in the workplace. In the findings of this research, Emotional Intelligence is unable to suppress CWB caused by work stress.

Keywords:- Counterproductive Work Behavior, Emotional Intelligence, Work Stress, Organizational Justice.

I. INTRODUCTION

Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB) is any employee behavior that can be detrimental to themselves or the organization (Spector & Fox, 2005). The behavior shown is often negative behavior, such as not being disciplined with time, often arriving late, liking to leave work, and having difficulty following applicable organizational rules (Robinson & Benner, 2000). Negative employee behavior will reduce the organization's functionality internally, increase huge costs, and reduce the productivity of the organization (Cohen, 2016). This will result in more complex problems for the organization. If this behavior is not suppressed by the organization, the organization will experience large losses financially.

Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB) is a problem for public and private sector organizations. Dick & Rayner (2013); Novrianti (2014) in Pratama & Parahyanti (2019) states that the level of CWB in public sector organizations is higher compared to the private sector. In Indonesia, many government employees, in this case Civil Servants (PNS), show Counterproductive Work Behavior. CWB is common among civil servants, such as frequently not being present at work, being lazy, coming late, and being unproductive. According to Rusdi (2014), around 50% of the 4.7 million civil servants in Indonesia still have low quality. Widarani (2015) in his research stated that there are many types of work that can be done by a civil servant, but many employees do not work effectively, resulting in counterproductive work behavior such as playing on the computer during working hours or leaving the office during break times.

There are two main factors that cause the emergence of Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB) in employees, namely internal and external factors. Internal factors come from the employees themselves, such as psychological, emotional and depression fatigue (Makhdoom et al., 2019). Meanwhile, external factors come from the organization, such as leadership behavior (Kessler et al., 2013), a dirty work environment (Huangfu, et al., 2017), high levels of supervision in the workplace which makes employees uncomfortable (Martin et al., 2016).

Daulay (2022), said that many factors can trigger impulse Mahdi, S., et al., (2018) stated that work stress can affect employee performance, including increasing the risk of engaging in counterproductive work behavior (CWB). Job stress can cause unpleasant feelings, such as discomfort, worry, and exhaustion, which can affect how employees respond to workplace situations. Work Stress can disrupt an employee's work-life and personal life balance, which can increase the risk of CWB. Employees who experience work stress feel too tired or lack focus on work, which can lead to unproductive behavior such as absenteeism, tardiness, or lack of concentration while working. Work stress stimulates negative emotions and then gives birth to counterproductive behavior. Marisa & Utami (2021) stated that excessive work pressure causes negative emotions to arise in individuals, which makes them tend to be cynical and rude towards other

individuals. Apart from that, work stress can also increase the risk of counterproductive behavior (Ma & Li (2019); Hidayah & Fajrianthi (2023). Meanwhile, Chand & Chand (2014) shows that physiological symptoms caused by work stress in organizations do not significantly influence CWB. .

Previous research shows that there is still a gap in the relationship between work stress and CWB. This is because there are other factors that influence work stress and CWB. Emotional intelligence (EI) has been identified as one of the variables that influences CWB (Farrastama et al., 2019). Efendy (2005) defines a person's ability to recognize other people's emotions as empathy. Furnham (1997); Jung & Yoon (2012); Miao et al., (2017), employees with high levels of EI are less likely to be involved in activities related to CWB compared to employees with low levels of EI. Employees with high EI tend to be better able to manage their own emotions and respond better to the emotions of others. They are better able to collaborate with others and resolve conflicts in a positive and productive way. Therefore, they are less likely to exhibit self-defeating behavior at work.

Based on gaps in previous research, researchers are interested in conducting research on the influence of Work Stress on Counterproductive Work Behavior which is moderated by emotional intelligence in employees of the Central Lombok District Health Service.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB)

Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB) is negative or unproductive behavior carried out by employees that is not in line with the interests of the organization, is illegitimate in nature, and is detrimental to both the organization and the individual himself (Sackett, 2002). Spector & Fox (2005) further stated that CWB is a behavior that occurs based on individual will and tends to endanger the organization and the employees within it. Ones & Viewsvaran (2003) define CWB into four categories of deviant behavior which include: a) deviating from organizational goals; b) disruptive (disruptive); c) not complying with organizational norms and anti-social; d) hindering productive behavior. This definition is in line with that put forward by Robinson & Bennet (1995), CWB is work-deviant behavior that violates organizational norms and has the potential to harm the organization and organizational members carried out by the organizational members themselves.

Furthermore, Kelloway (2010) sees CWB as part of a protest carried out by employees against the organization, and this can occur individually or in groups. Meanwhile, Cullen and Sackett (2003) view CWB as an ineffective employee response to stressful work conditions. On the other hand, Penney and Spector (2005) view CWB as a form of violation committed by employees because of the employee's discomfort in the organization. Robinson & Bennett (1995) formulated the Counterproductive Work Behavior typology into two dimensions based on the level of seriousness (minor vs. serious) and the level of target behavior (intrapersonal vs. organizational). Based on these two dimensions, CWB is

classified into four indicators including 1) Production Deviations, and 2) Property Deviations. Political Deviance. 3) Political Deviations. 4) Personal Aggression.

Production deviations are included in the minor-organization deviance dimension, namely employee behavior that violates existing organizational rules or norms, but on a relatively small scale. These deviations include minor violations of internal policies. Property deviance is included in actions (serious-organizational deviance) is behavior that seriously violates organizational rules and norms relating to organizational assets and property. Political deviance is included in minor-interpersonal deviance. This deviation refers to individual behavior which involves social interactions that are not in line with social norms and rules in the workplace. Personal aggression refers to the most serious form of deviance (serious-interpersonal deviance), which involves physically or emotionally aggressive or harmful behavior towards other individuals in the workplace. For example including sexual harassment, physical violence, physical threats, intimidation, or extreme humiliation.

B. Work Stress

Sager (1991) defines work stress as a psychological state felt by someone when facing urgent but uncertain demands. This definition highlights that Work Stress can arise when someone faces complex work problems that do not have a clear solution, as well as an inability to cope with work demands due to limited abilities, resources or motivation. Lechat & Torres (2016) argue that work stress is influenced by individual characteristics and stressor stimuli. This emphasizes that each individual can react differently to stressful situations at work. Some people are more susceptible to stress than others, depending on their personal characteristics and the type of job demands they face.

Work stress can also have a negative impact on general health conditions. Stress at work can appear in the form of fear, anxiety, or nervousness, as stated by Lazarus & Folkman (1984) and Desa et al., (2014). This shows that emotional reactions to work stress can involve a variety of negative feelings that can affect an individual's mental and physical well-being. Setyono et al., (2007) stated that a stressor or source of stress is a necessary prerequisite for a stress response to occur. Stressors arise through environmental factors. In other words, stressors are factors from the environment that can trigger a stress response in individuals.

Yao et al., (2014) define Work Stress as a biological response or reaction that tends to be constant in a person's body. This response is influenced by stimuli or stressors originating from the environment. Work stress is then produced by the emergence of work-related stressors on individuals and their environment, as well as interactions between the two. Individual responses to stressors and the relationship between the two play a role in the formation of stress. Fox et al., (2001) differentiated two types of work stressors in the context of work stress. The first is interpersonal conflict at work, such as arguments or rude treatment from coworkers. Second, stressors originating from the organization, such as excessive work demands,

incompatibility with work equipment, or an uncomfortable work environment. Both can create stressful situations in the workplace.

C. Emotional Intelligence

Salovey & Mayer (1990) were the first to propose the concept of emotional intelligence. Salovey & Mayer (1990) describe it as a form of social intelligence that involves the ability to monitor and manage feelings and emotions, both in oneself and in others. Goleman (1995) adopted Salovey & Mayer's (1990) definition, and proposed that emotional intelligence involves the ability for self-awareness, emotional management, self-motivation, empathy for others, and skills in managing social relationships.

Mayer & Salovey (1997) conceptualized emotional intelligence into four different dimensions: understanding emotions, evaluating emotions, using emotions, and regulating emotions. As stated by Agrawal (2020), EI involves the accurate perception, understanding, and regulation of one's own emotions and the emotions of others, and includes active and purposeful integration of feelings and thoughts. This ability to manage emotions can take the form of the ability to deal with frustration, so that employees can think clearly and professionally even under work pressure (Walker et al., 2022).

H1: Work Stress has a positive and significant influence on CWB

H2: Emotional Intelligence weakens the influence of Work Stress on CWB.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is quantitative research with a causal associative approach. Causal research is a type of research conducted to determine the cause-and-effect relationship between two or more variables to determine whether changes in one variable affect changes in other variables (Umar, 2005). This research involves measuring the relationship between exogenous and endogenous variables as well as intervening variables which are expressed using numbers or a numerical scale. Samples were taken using the Non-Probability Sampling census method where all members of the population were sampled. The population in this study were all Civil Servants of the Central Lombok District Health Service, totaling 112 employees consisting of 61 employees with civil servant status and 51 employees with non-PNS status. The data collection technique uses a questionnaire with a 1 – 5 Likert scale questionnaire. The questionnaire items consist of 47 questions, 16 CWB questions (Benneth & Robinson, 2000), 15 Work Stress questions (Robbins, 2015), and 16 Emotional Intelligence questions (Wong & Law, 2002).

IV. RESULTS

Outer loading is an indicator used to describe how well the items in a measurement model measure the variable. A high outer loading value indicates that the items are strongly connected to the variable being measured. Rule of thumb

according to Chin, (1998), an outer loading value > 0.50 is acceptable (valid).

Based on Figure 1, it can be seen that all measurement items for each variable, including the Work Stress, Emotional Intelligence and Counterproductive Work Behavior variables, show an outer loading value of > 0.5, so it can be said that all the indicators used are valid.

Composite Reliability is a measure to show how far the variables being measured correlate with each other, while Average Variance Extracted shows how far the variables can explain the variation in the measurement items as a whole.

Table 1. Composite Reliability dan AVE

Variabel	Composite Reliability	Average variance extracted (AVE)
CWB	0,962	0,616
EI	0,987	0,825
EI x WS -> CWB	1,000	1,000
WS	0,975	0,737

Based on the results of data analysis in Table 1, it show that all research variables, CWB, WS, and EI, have high Composite Reliability values, namely more than 0.7. This shows that the items measuring the variable are consistent in measuring the variable in question. Apart from that, all research variables also have good AVE values, namely more than 0.5. This shows that the items measuring these variables have a high correlation with each other.

To test the structural model hypothesis, bootstrapping (percentile method) was carried out. The statistical test used is the t-test. The t-value for the two-tailed test is 1.96, which is a critical value at the 5% significance level. The testing criteria with the t-test are if the value of *tstatistik* > *ttabel* or significance value < 0.05 then the hypothesis is accepted, but if *tstatistik* < *ttabel* or significance value > 0.05 then the null hypothesis is rejected.

This research uses a Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis approach to test the research hypothesis that was stated previously. Hypothesis testing can be done through t-statistic values and probability values through Bootstrapping which can be seen in the following figure:

Fig 1. Path Coefficient

Table 4. Hypothesis Test Results

Relationship between variables	Coefficient Track	T Statistic	P Value
Work Stress > CWB	0,713	16,932	0,000
EI X WS > CWB	-0,58	1,275	0,393

Based on Table 2 above, the relationship between variables (hypothesis test results) can be explained. Firstly, Work Stress has a positive and significant effect on Counterproductive Work Behavior with a coefficient value of 0.713, a t statistic value of 16.932 > 1.96, and a P value of 0.000 < 0.05 so that hypothesis 1 (H1) is accepted. Second, Emotional Intelligence does not moderate the influence of work stress on Counterproductive Work Behavior with a coefficient value of -0.58, a t statistic value of 1.275 < 1.96, and a P value of 0.393 > 0.05 so that hypothesis 2 (H2) is rejected. This means that high or low levels of Emotional Intelligence have no effect on CWB caused by Work Stress.

The R square value is used to measure the overall influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable in the model. The following is a table of R square values in this research:

Table 3 R square value

Variable	R-square
CWB	0,721

Table 3 shows that the influence of Work Stress and Organizational Justice on Counterproductive Work Behavior is 72.1%, which is included in the high category.

The F square value is used to measure how much influence exogenous variables have on endogenous variables. The following is a table of F square values in this study:

Table 4. Nilai F Square

Variable	CWB
Work Stress	1,147

Table 4 shows that Work Stress has a high influence (F square = 1.147) on Counterproductive Work Behavior.

The Q square value is used to measure how well the model can predict (predictive relevance) endogenous variables. A high Q square value indicates that the model can predict endogenous variables well. The Q square value can be seen in Table 5 below:

Table 5. Nilai Q square

Variable	Q Square
CWB	0,698

Table 5 shows a Q square value of 0.698, which means that the variables that influence CWB have high predictive relevance to the CWB variable. Every change or variation in the CWB variable can be predicted by the Work Stress variable.

Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) is a measure to measure how big the difference is between the correlation of empirical data and the correlation of the estimated model results. SRMR values can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. SRMR Result

Item	Estimated model
SRMR	0.060

The SRMR value of this research model is 0.060, which is smaller than 0.10. According to [38], SRMR values below 0.10 are still acceptable. Therefore, the model built in this study fits the empirical data.

V. DISCUSSION

A. The Effect of Work Stress on Counterproductive Work Behavior

The research findings show that there is a positive and significant influence between Work Stress on Counterproductive Work Behavior with a coefficient value of 0.713, a t statistic value of 16.932 > 1.96, and a P value of 0.000 < 0.05. This means that the higher the Work Stress, the higher the level of Counterproductive Work Behavior carried out by employees. Vice versa, if employee work stress is lower, the level of counterproductive work behavior will also be lower. The results of this research are also in line with several previous research results conducted by Salami (2010), Ma & Li (2019), Farrastama et al., (2019), De Clercq et al., (2019), Destriana & Dewi (2021) in where work stress has a positive and significant effect on CWB.

Pressure in the workplace can not only give rise to negative affectivity in employees, which in turn leads to behavior that is detrimental to the organization (CWB). This finding is in accordance with the concept of Jobs Demands-Resources Theory (JD-R) developed by Bakker & Demerouti (2017). According to the JD-R Theory, a work environment that combines job demands and job resources will influence employee welfare and productivity. Workload includes elements such as pressure, high work demands, and work stress. This theory emphasizes that when workload exceeds available resources, employees will experience job stress, which in turn can lead to counterproductive work behavior.

Individual perceptions of negative or detrimental circumstances greatly influence their attitudes and behavior (Moore, 2000). Work stressors can produce pressure or strain on individuals, and this strain can have an impact on various aspects, including behavioral disorders, psychological disorders, and physical disorders (Krischer et al., 2010). CWB is a form of coping in the form of counterproductive behavior that appears as a response to reduce the negative impact of pressure and stress in the workplace (Spector & Fox, 2006).

B. Moderation of Emotional Intelligence on the influence of Work Stress on Counterproductive Work Behavior

The research results show that Emotional Intelligence does not moderate (weaken) the influence of Work Stress on Counterproductive Work Behavior with a coefficient value of -0.58, a t statistic value of 1.275 < 1.96, and a P value of

0.393 > 0.05. This means that high or low levels of Emotional Intelligence will not affect CWB caused by Work Stress.

The relationship between Work Stress, EI, and CWB can be much more complex than EI alone can capture. Work stress can come from various sources, including high work pressure (Mangkunegara, 2002), interpersonal conflict (Ilies et al., 2011), or feelings of injustice in the organization (Febrianti & Syarifah, 2022). These factors affect individuals differently and are influenced by a variety of other additional factors. Therefore, EI's ability to moderate this relationship may be limited because it only measures part of this complexity.

Every individual experiences fluctuations in their moods and emotions (Jordon, 2002). They have varying levels of EI, and this can cause variability in their ability to manage stress. A high level of emotional intelligence in employees does not guarantee that they will not engage in deviant behavior (CWB) in the workplace (Yadav & Rai, 2020). However, because EI can range from low to high levels, not all individuals with high levels of EI will have similar responses to stress. These results indicate that although emotional intelligence can help reduce the negative impact of work stress, work stress still has a significant influence on counterproductive work behavior.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the research analysis and the results of the discussion in the previous chapter, the conclusions of this research are as follows: (1) Work Stress has a positive and significant effect on Counterproductive Work Behavior. (2) Emotional Intelligence does not moderate the influence of work stress on Counterproductive Work Behavior.

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